

People Power And Alternative Politics

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Abstract

In the developing world over the last few decades people power' movements emerged to challenge the 'authoritarian logic' of undemocratic regimes as well as the dominant 'development logic' promoted by the Governments of developed countries international economic institutions, and multinational corporations. This article looks at people power movements that challenged political authoritarianism in the Philippines and Myanmar, and people power movements that challenge development policies in India. Thailand, and Brail. It explains how these social movements mobilise people and generate pressure for social change. 'For pragmatic or principled reasons, people power movements incorporate methods of non-violent action in struggles against Governments, large landowners, and corporations. Drawing on environmentalist, sustainable development discourses, they promote democratization and alternative visions of development.

Key words- Social movements, people power movement, divergent outcomes.

Introduction

In many parts of the developing world, grass-roots movements have emerged as a political force to be reckoned with. People excluded from politics are increasingly engaging in organized collective action to defend their livelihoods, promote a more equitable distribution of land and resources, challenge state and corporate-driven development policies, and advance democratization. From the 1980s onward, citizens in numerous authoritarian regimes mobilized campaigns of non-violent resistance to challenge the entrenched political elite and promote democratization (Schock 2005). Marginalized peoples suffering from negative consequences of the 'development project' and the **globalization** project of **neo-liberalism** (McMichael 2008) struggle against deforestation, over-fishing, industrial and export agriculture, large dam projects, and increasing land inequality. Furthermore, resistance is mobilized against neo-liberal economic policies and the 'new enclosures' (Harvey 2003; Shiva 2005), such as the privatization of public utilities and resources, and an intellectual property rights regime that contributes to the **privatization** and **commodification** of resources and traditional knowledge of peasants and indigenous peoples.

Social Movements And People Power

Social movements are collective, organized and sustained efforts to promote social change that occur partially or entirely outside conventional politics. Their participants are often drawn from marginalized segments of Society that are excluded from decision-making processes. Thus, they must engage in

extra-institutional methods of political action to exert political influence. These methods may be violent, non-violent, or a combination of the two.

Examples Of Non-Violent Actionist

Protest and persuasion
Protest demonstrations
Marches
Political rallies
Public speeches
Declarations
Vigils

People Power Movements And Democratization

People power movements have contributed to democratization in some parts of the developing world, including South America (Bolivia, Brazil, Uruguay, Chile and Peru), the Caribbeans (Haiti), Africa (Sudan, Benin, South Africa, Mali, Madagascar, and Nigeria), Asia (Philippines, South Korea, Taiwan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Thailand, Mongolia, and Indonesia), the Middle East (Lebanon), and the former Soviet Union (Georgia, Ukraine, and Fyrgyzstan). In some of these countries democracy took root; others subsequently experienced democratization and a slide back to overt authoritarianism. Comparable pro-democracy movements in other places failed to promote democratization, Pakistan, Myanmar, Tibet, and China were brutally crushed. Below, two pro-democracy people power movements are discussed: a successful one (the Philippines) and an unsuccessful one (Myanmar).

Myanmar: The 8-8-88 Pro-Democracy Movement

Myanmar has been ruled by a military dictatorship since 1962, when General Ne Win assumed power in a coup against the democratic regime of U Nu. The alleged justification for the military takeover included a perceived turning away from the state's founding socialist principles, U Nu's policy of establishing Buddhism as the state religion, and his negotiations with leaders of non-Burman states for greater autonomy, inviting attempts to exercise their constitutional right to secede. Upon declaring martial law, Ne Win expanded the role of the military in the polity economy. The Burma Socialist Programme Party (BSPP) was formed as a means of mass mobilization and political indoctrination. All other political parties were banned and potential political rivals were eliminated. The result has been gross inefficiency, rampant corruption, and economic decline.

Divergent Outcomes

What accounts for the divergent outcomes of the two pro-democracy people power movements? Characteristics of the movements themselves as well as the political context each played a role (Schock 1999; 2005). In the Philippines, two broad-based organizations emerged to coordinate the unarmed struggle against Marcos, namely Baya (Bagong Alyansang Makabayan) and the United Democratic Opposition (UNIDO). Bayan acted as an umbrella organization, coordinating the activities of a diverse array of progressive organizations promoting the interest of women, peasants, and workers. UNIDO, representing the traditional political elite opposition and its middle-class followers, acted as both a political party and a social movement organization, engaging in both non-violent action and electoral activity. Both strands of the anti-Marcos challenge implemented varied non-violent actions and responded innovatively to Government repression. General strikes, civil disobedience, and the rejection of the official election results undermined the state's power and legitimacy. These actions, along with the growing armed communist insurgency in the countryside, promote capital flight, contributed to sever ties to Marcos and throw its weight behind Corazon Aquino.

India: Ekta Parishad²

A variety of social movements in India address issues related to the control over and access to land and natural resources, including movements concerned with bio piracy, deforestation, dam building, indigenous people's rights, land reform, and agricultural policy. Ekta Parishad (Unity Forum), a Gandhian land rights organization of founded in 1990, struggles to prevent land alienation and to promote the access of marginalized people to livelihood natural resources. Its members are drawn from the most disadvantaged segments of society, such as lower-caste farmers and rural workers and adivasis. Adivasis are indigenous tribal peoples in India who traditionally inhabit forestland.

Thailand: Assembly Of The Poor³

The Assembly of the Poor (Samatcha khon chon) is composed of various groups adversely affected by development policies implemented by the Thai state to promote industrialization, export-oriented agriculture, and commercial forestry. A substantial promotion come from the hundreds of thousands of rural and forest-dwelling people who have been adversely affected by the construction of large-scale dams, which have caused the loss of fisheries and the flooding of land upon which people depend for their livelihoods. The government has often failed to adequately compensate displaced people for their losses.

Brazil: The Landless Rural Workers' Movement (Mst)

Brazil has one of the highest levels of lands inequality in the world, a legacy of Portuguese colonization and the continued political influence of the land owning elite. The 1964 and statute Act and the 1988 Brazilian Constitution specify that the government has the responsibility to redistribute land that is not being productively used, but no serious land reform programme has been implemented. In fact a progressive government that was considering land reforms was removed by a US government-backed military coup in 1964. From the 1970s onward, the number of landless people and unemployed rural workers increased due to the building of several hydroelectric dams, the expansion of large industrial farms for export agriculture, and the implementation of policies favouring

large-scale farming and contributing to the indebtedness of small farmers. Disillusioned peasants began taking over unproductively used land through unarmed land occupations. Further land occupations were subsequently organized by the Landless Rural Workers' Movement, or the MST (Movement of dos Trabalhadores Rurais Sem Terra), a social movement organization that was officially founded in 1984. The MST originated in Brazil's southern most states, Rio Grande do Sul, Santa Catarina and Parana, growing out of a network of progressive members of the Catholic Church who practised **liberation theology** and Marxist activists concerned with rural violence and inequality.

Politics Of Alternative Development

The development policies implemented by many developing countries over the past half-century have prioritized constructing large dams, promoting industrial farming and export-oriented agriculture, and extracting timber and minerals. These policies have contributed to the displacement of people, the privatization of communal land and resources, increasing level of land inequality, and environmental degradation. They have threatened the material bases of small farmers, landless rural workers, and indigenous peoples. In response, social movements with strong critiques of the dominant models of development have mobilized and pursued goals consistent with environmentalism, sustainable development, and grass-roots democracy. Social movements, like those discussed above, not only resist destructive policies. They also challenge entrenched systems of inequality and traditional rural social relations such as authoritarianism, violence, and patriarchy, with traditional caste relations in India and traditional patron-client in both Thailand and Brazil being good examples. All three organizations promote gender equality and empower people to take a stand against corruption, violence, and traditional deference to authority.

Conclusion

From the 1980s onward, a wave of people power movements challenged authoritarian regimes throughout the developing world. Many movements contributed to human rights and democratization. Less dramatically, but perhaps more importantly, people power movements have also emerged

through the developing world to challenge the dominant development logic and neo-liberal economic policies. Drawing on human rights, environmentalism, and sustainable development discourses, these movements are increasingly becoming linked through transnational networks.

References:

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Web Links

1. www.ektaparishad.com Ekta Parishad, Bhopal, India; contains information about the history and activities of India's Ekta Parishad (unity forum).
2. www.mst.org.br Movimento dos Trabalhadores Rurais Sem Terra, Sao Paulo, Brazil; contains information about the history and activities of Brazil's MST.